

Present status of *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) in South Africa (Araneae: Pholcidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) is a widespread, pantropical spider known for its very long legs, squarish abdomen, and close association with human structures. It is harmless to humans and often considered beneficial because it preys on mosquitoes and other small arthropods. The original range of *C. lyoni* is unknown and they have been introduced into different parts of the world accidentally and are now pantropical in distribution. It was the first time reported from South Africa in 2009 from the Tshwane Market where they were regarded as a problem due to the large amounts of unsightly webs they construct on the walls. The presented status and distribution in South Africa is discussed, with notes on the general morphology and notes on their lifestyle.

Keywords: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa), cosmopolitan

INTRODUCTION

In 2009, the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) Spider Identification Services received queries from the Tshwane fresh produce market in Gauteng about a spider invasion causing problems. On inspection, we found clusters of unsightly webbing in the corners of the walls and ceiling (Figs 3 & 4). Spiders were present in large numbers in unsightly webs on the walls in most of the halls at the market. The webbing collects dust and dirt, and at a high cost, it is removed annually, but without long-term success. The control was unsuccessful mainly because the spiders escaped by dropping to the ground when anything touched their webs.

Specimens sampled were identified as a Pholcidae species *Crossopriza lyoni* (Blackwall, 1867) (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009). The species has a widespread, pantropical distribution throughout the warmer parts of the world (Huber, 2022) and is recognised by its long legs, rectangular abdomen, and close association with human structures (Figs 1 & 2).

TAXONOMY

The genus *Crossopriza* (Simon, 1893) comprises 24 species (World Spider Catalog, 2026), of which five are recorded from Africa. It has ecological requirements similar to those of *Smeringopus*, but while the latter occurs in Southern and Eastern Africa, *Crossopriza* (5 species in Africa) is restricted to Northern Africa, with additional species on the Arabian Peninsula.

Crossopriza lyoni (Blackwall, 1867) has the widest distribution in Africa, but it also seems to be restricted to the north (Huber, 2005; Huber *et al.*, 1999). The species has a long synonymy list due to historical reclassification and is presently listed in the World Spider Catalog (2026) as probably native to Africa and/or Asia and introduced to several countries.

Diagnostic characters: : Small to medium-sized. Carapace with a deep, round depression between the head and thorax, with a distinct pattern; eyes eight, occupying entire width of carapace; anterior median eyes smallest, with other eyes in two triads (Fig. 7). Abdomen high with a triangular appearance in lateral view, with caudal end tapering to a point above spinnerets; marked with a dark, irregular pattern (Figs 5 & 6). Legs thin and much longer than the body (often 8–10 times body length); often with faint dark bands or lines near the joints long (Figs 2 & 6). Females have an epigyne with a flat chitin plate without a movable ligula (Fig. 10). Male palp (Figs 8 & 9).

Figures 1–4. *Crossopriza lyoni*. 1. Female with egg sac. 2. Female collected at the Tshwane market. 3-4. Webbing causing the problems at the market. Credits: 1. Vida vd Walt and 2-4. Les Oates.

Figures 5–10. *Crossopriza lyoni*. 5. Abdomen lateral view. 6. Showing abdomen and long legs. 7. Eye pattern. 8–9. Male palp. 10. Epigyne. Credits: 5–8. A. Dippenaar-Schoeman. 9–10. After Huber (2022).

DISTRIBUTION

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Probably native to Africa and/or Asia. Introduced to the Americas, Belgium, Germany, Australia, Micronesia.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: The report on the species sampled in Tshwane (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2009) was the first record of the species from South Africa. But observations presently available on iNaturalist (2018-2026) show that the species has a wider distribution in South Africa and was observed in the Limpopo, Mpumalanga, and Western Cape provinces (Fig. 11). Research-grade observations were mainly from records in and around the Kruger National Park, as well as in the Soutpansberg. Only three observations are from the Western Cape (Fig. 11).

From iNaturalist the species seems to occur also observed in other southern African countries such as Botswana, Namibia, Mozambique and Zimbabwe.

Figure 11. Map showing the distribution of *Crossopriza lyoni* research grade observations on iNaturalist (green) downloaded on 15/3/2026. Credit: Wynand Uys.

LIFESTYLE

The species lives in space-webs found in a variety of habitats that are usually dark and shady, such as caves, holes, and crevices. However, *C. lyoni* was found in South Africa in and around buildings such as garages or storerooms. Their webs are made of non-sticky silk and often appears irregular and looks untidy, and loose (Figs 3 & 4). The spider hangs upside-down underneath the more dense part of the web. When disturbed, the spider vibrates it rapidly and was seen dropping to the ground. The eggs (40-50) are formed into a ball are held together by a few silken threads and are carried in the chelicerae of the female (Fig. 1).

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